

Relationship of Organisational Culture and Organisational Commitment with Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

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Organisational Culture exerts a significant influence on how employees of an organisation think and act. Culture has been found to associate directly as well as indirectly with Organisational Citizenship Behaviour, which has often been considered as one of the indices of organisational effectiveness and performance. Literature suggests that certain kinds of organisational culture promote organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). Also, organisational commitment has exhibited a positive influence on extra-role behavior like OCB. The purpose of this paper was precisely to investigate the relationship between organisational culture values (Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Authenticity, Proaction, Autonomy, Collaboration & Experimentation) and organizational commitment with OCB. A survey method was used for collecting data from 295 participants, who belonged to private and public sectors of three different types of organisations, namely, banks, construction companies and schools. OCTAPACE Profile by Pareek and Rao (1992) was used to assess organisational culture. Organizational commitment was measured using a scale by Mayer et al. (1993) with three types of commitment- affective, normative and continuance. Organisational citizenship behaviour scale, comprising four dimensions- Helping, Initiating, Defending and Refraining was developed by the researcher. Correlation, regression and mediation analysis were performed. The findings pointed out that OCTAPACE values as well as types of commitment could predict OCB dimensions with large variances in them in most of the organisations. It means OCTAPACE values perceived by employees and commitment of the employees towards their organisation will lead them to engage in OCB. However, certain specific relationships between the constructs were negative or non-significant. Findings were interpreted and their implications and limitations were discussed.

Keywords: OCTAPACE values, organisational citizenship behaviour, commitment, prediction

'Culture is not an initiative. Culture is the enabler of all initiatives.'

- Larry Senn

Despite the recent conversation on novel concepts like compulsory citizenship behavior, researchers' enthusiasm regarding organisational citizenship behavior has not faded. OCB continues to be researched owing to its productive value for organisations.

Results of past research allow us to view organisational culture as an important dynamic organisational-level antecedent of organisational citizenship behaviour. Culture comes up as people of an organisation learn adaptation with change in the artefacts, customs, setup of space, furniture arrangement, and ways of dealing with various processes and phenomena. It gives people accepted ways of expressing and affirming their beliefs, values and norms (Trice & Beyer, 1993). In other words, "*cultures are a natural outgrowth of the social interactions that make up what we call organizations*" (Trice & Beyer, 1993). Though many researches are being conducted on organisational culture, very little agreement on the concept and definition of culture is there. Studies have used

different jargons and terms and the same terms have been used with different meanings (Pareek, 2002). Culture-related concepts are values, ethics, beliefs, environment, atmosphere, climate, ethos, etc. These terms have been used vaguely and interchangeably, though efforts have been made to define some of them clearly (Pareek, 1991). Schein (1985) highlighted the role of values in bringing about internal integration. When values are shared, employees get encouraged to interact with greater efficiency (Kluckhohn, 1951). Values have been defined as wanted trans-situational goals that act as guiding principles in the lives of individuals (Schwartz, 1992) including workplace behaviors (Schwartz, 1999).

Relationship between Organisational Culture and Organisational Citizenship Behavior

Organisational culture exerts great but hidden and indirect pressure to tailor our thoughts and behavior in certain specific ways. It has been regarded as a crucial determinant of organisational effectiveness (Deal & Kennedy, 1982; Ouchi, 1983). Numerous researchers and scholars (Deal & Kennedy, 1983; Cameron & Freeman, 1991) in the field of organisational studies emphasize that an organisation with a strong and congruent culture is far more effective than one with a weak, incongruent, and disconnected culture. Research has repeatedly shown that organisational culture is directly as well as indirectly related to organisational citizenship behavior. OCB has often been considered one of the tenets, criteria, or indicators of organisational effectiveness and performance.

Organisational culture is measurable and associated with important organisational outcomes. Organisational culture has been found to significantly impact a firm's long-term performance (Kotter

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& Heskett, 1992). It is explained in the form of influence that an organisation's culture has on the behaviour of its employees. One such behavior is OCB. Paine and Organ (2000) noted that the perception of OCB and performance is viewed by cultural aspects like power-distance and social stratification in an organisation. Research by Denison and his colleagues (Denison & Mishra, 1995) has demonstrated that an empirical relationship exists between culture and organisational performance in different contexts employing varied performance criteria. The relationship between organisational culture and effectiveness was studied by them with the help of case studies and a survey method.

Organisational cultural values also influence OCB because culture is a showcase of the values, beliefs, and behavioral norms that people employ in an organisation to give meaning to and understand the situations that they encounter; it has the potential to impact the attitudes and behaviour of the employees. The prime reason for examining cultural values is that these values affect people's attitudes and behaviour (Schwartz, 1999). Values hold special importance as they manifest in behavioral norms, directly affecting the organisation's functioning. Pareek and Rao (1992) have talked about eight values important for institution building, also called the culture profile of the organisation. These are openness, confrontation, trust, authenticity, proaction, autonomy, collaboration, and experimentation. These values are considered as steps to create a functional ethos and for promoting organisational growth. The priorities given to these values will affect how an individual interprets a situation and how he or she reacts and behaves in situations (Schwartz, 1996). A similar opinion was given by Schwartz et al. (2000) according to whom values can influence how an individual perceives and interprets a given situation and the importance he or she gives it. Each person defines a situation in the light of key values important to him or her. The eight values discussed by Pareek and Rao (2002) also seem to relate to extra-role behaviour like OCB.

Relationship between Organisational Commitment and Organisational Citizenship Behavior

Organisational commitment is conceptualized as the psychological attachment of the employee to his or her organization. Scholl (1981) suggested that commitment helps keep the employee motivated towards work even in the absence of rewards. Thus, employees committed to the organization have a greater tendency to contribute to its goals and are more likely than others to make efforts beyond their required task performance to enhance the organisation's effectiveness. Mayer and Allen (1984) talked about three-component concept of organisational commitment: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

A strong, significant and positive relationship between organisational commitment and OCB has been indicated by empirical evidence. Organisational commitment has been considered as an important predictor of OCB for a long time (Meyer et al., 2002). Scholl (1981) emphasised that organisational commitment is responsible for behaviour that is not basically driven by reinforcement or punishment. Thus, OCB, which encompasses a personal involvement in the life of an organisation, is also assumed to be influenced by commitment. Organisational commitment not only shares a strong relationship with OCB but also has a

relationship with organisational factors of culture, structure, and HRM practices. These constructs have been discussed by organisational behaviour researchers for a long time, though no substantial effort has been made to study them in conjunction. The literature hints at their plausible relationship. Thus, OCB, which essentially involves personal involvement in the organisation's life, is also assumed to be influenced by commitment.

Method

Participants

295 people working in various organisations of Delhi participated in the study. The percentage of males and females in the sample was 62.4% and 37.6%, respectively. Whereas, the ratio of various levels of management, i.e., higher, middle, and lower levels, was 12.5%, 55.6%, and 31.9%, respectively. The mean age of the respondents in the sample was 40 ($SD=9.8$), the mean tenure was 11 years ($SD=9.06$), and the mean annual emolument was Rs. 10.5 lakh ($SD=8.15$). The data represented a sample collected from six organisations with equal representation from the public and private sectors. Also, three different types of organizations were included in the study, namely, schools, banks, and construction companies.

Measures

Organisational Culture: It was understood in this study as the beliefs and values prevalent in the organisation. Organisational culture was measured using the OCTAPACE Profile by Pareek and Rao (1992). It assesses an organisation's culture using eight values openness, confrontation, trust, authenticity, proaction, autonomy, collaboration, and experimentation. These are composed of eight different dimensions of the measure. Each dimension has a combination of positive and negative item responses, which were to be given on a 4-point scale (4- high value to 1- very low value). The scale contains 40 items. It is divided into two parts. The first part asks about the values, whereas the second part asks about the beliefs prevailing in the organization. A high score on a dimension indicates stronger perceived beliefs and values in the organization and vice versa. The maximum score on the scale could be 40, and the minimum could be 160. However, the scores ranged between 1 and 4 as the mean scores for the culture values were found. Eleven items were reverse-coded (12,14, 22, 23, 25, 26, 28, 30, 31, 35, 40). A few changes were made in the second section of the scale to make it easier to understand. The split-half reliability of the scale was 0.81.

Organisational Commitment: It was measured using scales developed by Mayer et al. (1993). It measured three dimensions of organisational commitment- Affective, Normative and Continuance commitment. Affective commitment was conceptualized as members remaining in the organisation because they want to. Normative commitment was understood as members remaining with the organisation because they feel they ought to do so. In continuance commitment, members stay with the organisation because they need to remain with the organisation. It had a total of 18 items, its Cronbach alpha coefficient for the three scales being 0.83, 0.76 and 0.70 respectively.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior: It was understood in this study as employee behavior that is voluntary, not a part of an individual's job profile, neither directly nor explicitly recognized by the formal reward system. The absence of such behavior is not punishable but overall, they contribute positively to the effective

functioning of the organisation. A self-developed scale was used to measure this construct. The scale had 23 items, which measured four factors or dimensions of OCB. These were helping, initiating, defending, and refraining. Five items, i.e, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23 were reverse-coded. Responses to these items were to be given on a 5-point scale (1-rarely, 2-seldom, 3-sometimes, 4-often, 5-almost always). A high score on each dimension indicates high Helping, Initiating, Defending, and Refraining behavior, while a low score depicts the opposite. The Cronbach alpha was found to be .836 for the full scale.

Procedure

First, the organisations where data collection was to be conducted

were identified. Then, permission was obtained from the heads of these organisations to conduct the surveys. The respondents were personally contacted, and after their informed consent to participate in the study was obtained, they were informed how the questionnaire was to be filled out. They were allowed to take their own time to complete the questionnaires.

Results

The data obtained were responses marked on Likert scales. These were then entered into SPSS software, cleaned and prepared for analysis. After analysis of the data, the findings were presented. Correlation and regression analysis were performed along with descriptive analysis.

Table 1

Correlations among the Variables (Organizational Culture, Commitment and OCB)

	Affective	Normative	Continuance	Helping	Initiating	Defending	Refraining
Openness	.470**	.232**	-.044	.514**	.349**	.084	.285**
Confrontation	.431**	.144*	-.047	.505**	.087	.104	.106
Trust	.377**	.190**	.188**	.552**	.228**	.149*	.071
Authenticity	.121*	-.310**	-.050	.379**	-.301**	-.186**	-.169*
Proaction	.432**	.312**	.269**	.678**	.182**	.296**	-.004
Autonomy	-.170**	.163**	.083	-.476**	.265**	.131*	.021
Collaboration	.312**	.043	-.126*	.235**	.157**	.134*	.170**
Experimentation	.352**	.338**	.067	.425**	.317**	.151*	.176**
Affective	-	-	-	.406**	.273**	.420**	.488**
Normative	-	-	-	.117*	.635**	.545**	.221**
Continuance	-	-	-	.122*	.150**	.297**	-.408**

Table 1 shows how different dimensions of organisational culture relate to different types of organisational commitment and various dimensions of (OCB): helping, initiating, defending, and refraining behaviour. Openness shows strong positive correlations with affective commitment (.470), helping (.514), initiative (.349), and refraining (.285). It can be inferred that employees who perceive their organisation as fostering openness are more emotionally attached to it and are more likely to engage in OCBs. Confrontation correlates positively with affective commitment (.431) and helping behaviour (.505), suggesting that a culture that permits open discussion of conflict can encourage emotional involvement and helping behaviour. Trust correlates moderately with all forms of commitment and especially strongly with helping behaviour (.552), indicating that trust is a central aspect of OCB, especially cooperative actions. Authenticity has mixed effects while it shows a slight positive correlation with affective commitment (.121), it has negative correlations with normative commitment (-.310), initiating (-.301), and defending (-.186). It may suggest that authenticity may lessen initiative and internalized loyalty. Proactive culture is strongly correlated with helping (.678) and affective commitment (.432), showing that when organizations promote initiative-taking, it reflects in employees' positive attitudes and behavior. It was found that autonomy negatively correlated with affective commitment (-.170) and helping behaviour (-.476). This possibly indicates that independence after a certain limit may decrease cohesive and cooperative behavior. Also, it was found that collaboration has a weaker, but still significant positive correlation with helping (.235)

and initiating behaviour (.157). This suggests that collaborative values and environments in organisations encourage OCB. Experimentation proved to correlate positively with most outcomes, especially affective commitment (.352), normative commitment (.338), and initiating behaviour (.317). This indicates that a culture encouraging innovativeness supports both commitment and proactive behavior. On the other hand, affective commitment correlated positively with all four OCB dimensions, especially defending (.420) and refraining (.488), suggesting that loyalty and advocacy are predicted by emotional attachment. Normative commitment is highly correlated with initiating (.635) and defending (.545) behaviour, meaning internalized obligatory values influence responsible behaviour. Continuance commitment has weak and negative correlations with OCB, especially a negative correlation with refraining behavior (-.408), suggesting that OCB is not promoted if one stays in the employment just out of their need.

The helping dimension of OCB is best supported by cultural and commitment dimensions of trust, proactive culture, openness, and affective commitment, while autonomy or independence beyond a certain limit decreases helping behaviour. Taking initiatives in an organization greatly depends upon normative commitment, which may also be understood as internalized obligation, an open and experimental environment, and low authenticity. Defending the organisation is strongly influenced by emotional and moral commitment. When the employees of an organization feel emotionally connected, morally obligated, and perceive their workplace as open, collaborative, and innovative, they tend to advocate for their organization.

Table 2
Predictors of OCB (Helping, Initiating, Defending and Refraining)

Criterion variable ¹	Helping (Model-1)		Helping (Model-2)		Initiating (Model-1)		Initiating (Model-2)	
	Beta	t-value	Beta	t-value	Beta	t-value	Beta	t-value
Openness	.145	2.602**	.133	2.339**	.376	5.724**	.320	5.425**
Confrontation	.008	.145	-.007	-.121	-.166	-2.579**	-.162	-2.832**
Trust	.172	3.37**	.161	3.095**	.123	2.049*	.126	2.323*
Authenticity	.086	1.970**	.068	1.399	-.396	-7.718**	.187	-3.708**
Proaction	.450	8.19**	.444	7.369**	.052	.798	-.063	-1.012
Autonomy	-.246	-5.83**	-.229	-5.278**	.270	5.451**	-.176	3.884**
Collaboration	-.155	-2.58**	-.126	-2.716**	.088	1.673	.093	1.921
Experimentation	.017	-.351**	-.004	-.072	.245	4.329**	.124	2.39*
Affective			.124	2.43*			-.072	-1.365
Normative			-.082	-1.407			.525	8.614**
Continuance			.032	.267			-.109	-2.061*
R ²	.594		.603		.437		.569	
Adjusted R ²	.582		.587		.421		.552	
R ² Change	.594		.009		.437		.132	
F	52.268**		39.26**		27.71**		33.98**	
Criterion variable ¹	Defending (Model-1)		Defending (Model-2)		Refraining (Model-1)		Refraining (Model-2)	
	Beta	t-value	Beta	t-value	Beta	t-value	Beta	t-value
Openness	-.107	-1.381	-.185	-2.702**	.364	4.677**	.199	3.121**
Confrontation	.055	.725	.036	.548	-.031	-.402	-.156	-2.522*
Trust	.046	.652	-.027	-.434	-.031	-.442	.036	.619
Authenticity	-.298	-4.921**	-.130	-2.23*	-.278	-4.576**	-.166	-3.036**
Proaction	.402	5.252**	.170	2.342*	-.256	-3.344**	-.150	-2.218*
Autonomy	.169	2.877**	.098	1.867	-.035	-.601	.009	.181
Collaboration	.065	1.044	.082	1.461	.227	3.364**	.053	1.020
Experimentation	.031	.469	-.045	-.744	.154	2.296*	.067	1.205
Affective			.352	5.763**			.374	6.524**
Normative			.275	3.893**			.198	3.003**
Continuance			.159	2.593**			-.434	-.759
R ²	.213		.421		.211		.496	
Adjusted R ²	.191		.399		.189		.476	
R ² Change	.213		.208		.211		.285	
F	9.696**		18.708**		9.564**		25.317**	

Discussion

Organisational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), or any behaviour for that matter, does not take place in a vacuum, but occurs and gets influenced by several levels of organisational culture, values, and interpersonal dynamics. These correlated constructs may be conceptualized as multi-layered components of culture. The base or the first level consists of the values that make a group distinct from others, i.e., its own identity, often called 'ethos'. This ethos comprises the basic character or spirit of culture, which is shaped by the customs, beliefs and practices shared by the people. Underlying these are core values that define and guide employees' behaviour in the organization.

One core value among these is openness. Openness involves free, non-defensive sharing and receiving of feelings, thoughts, and ideas. It works bidirectionally and consists of spatial accessibility. This supports transparency in the organizations and helps create a psychologically safe environment. The climate of openness has been

found to predict important dimensions of OCB. These results point out that openness promotes cooperative and proactive behaviour, nurturing an organisational culture in which employees tend to engage in altruistic and conscientious behaviour (Mohanty & Rath, 2012). This confirms the findings of Moorman and Blakely (1995) stating that collectivist cultures, in which openness is central, promote citizenship behaviour.

When analysed constructively, it can be observed that even confrontation can be instrumental in shaping OCB. Conceptualized as facing problems head-on and indulging in interpersonal communication and analysis rather than avoidance of issues, confrontation can become an instrument for conflict resolution and obtaining clarity. Results suggest that constructive confrontation, used along with exploration, promotes helping by enhancing mutual understanding and trust. On the other hand, if confrontation is viewed negatively and is predicted pessimistically, it may point to the fact that confrontation can cause discomfort and hamper proactive behaviour in the absence of solution-focused dialogue.

This complex finding confirms the conclusion drawn by Kar and Tiwari (1999) that different elements of organizational culture have varied effects on specific dimensions of OCB.

Another important construct is trust, defined here not in moral, but functional terms. This involves maintaining confidentiality in matters, honouring mutual obligations and accepting others' statements at face value. Trust was found to significantly predict helping and initiating behaviour positively. The presence of an environment of trust creates an assurance in interpersonal relationships and makes the social fabric of organisations even stronger. Organ (1983) also laid great emphasis on the idea that job satisfaction and fairness are crucial antecedents of OCB, and that trust plays a key role in enhancing both of these.

Authenticity is the congruence of one's feelings, thoughts and actions and has also been found to contribute to OCB. It is expressed as owning up to one's mistakes and reducing the gaps between one's stated values and behaviour. Though difficult to explain on the face, it may be understood that too much authenticity may sometimes lead to undesirable realisations at times and hence lead to withdrawal of extra-role behavior like OCB dimensions such as initiating, defending, and refraining behaviour.

Similar to proactive behavior is proaction. This dimension of organisational culture involves planning, taking action and evaluating potential outcomes before taking any action. A proactive culture in the organization, which can foresee issues in advance, strongly predicts likely helping and defending behaviour, as was also the finding of this study. Though proaction negatively predicted refraining behaviour in places, this might suggest that initiative without any collaboration may not necessarily lead to advocacy. Such findings reconfirm the observation of Bhuiyan and Menguc (2002) according to whom autonomy, a component of proactivity, may lead to higher job satisfaction and, hence, OCB as well.

Coming to autonomy, which is defined as the will to use one's power without any fear and to empower others, shows a dual influence on OCB. On one hand, it was found to positively influence initiative and defending; on the other hand, it was seen as negatively predicting helping. These findings suggest that ownership and accountability are fostered by autonomy in the organisation. However, it reduces mutual interdependence. Similar findings were reported by Anderson and Williams (1996) who concluded that when associated with interdependence, autonomy promotes helping, which is based on exchange only. This underscores the idea that sole autonomy is not sufficient for promoting helping behaviour.

OCB is also promoted by Collaboration, i.e., the cultural value of collectively making efforts to workout problems and achieve shared goals. This encompasses sharing concerns, making strategies, and executing a plan of action together. Collaboration was found to sufficiently and directly predict OCB. Hence, it can be said that loyalty and organizational representation are facilitated by a culture of collaboration. This finding was also supported by Kar and Tiwari (1999) who highlighted that teamwork is important in promoting civic virtue and courtesies.

Organisational growth and factors associated with it are supported by experimentation, a cultural value that involves encouraging innovation and exploring innovative solutions to problems. It was found that experimentation positively predicted initiating and refraining dimensions of OCB. This suggests that organisational cultures which are open to experimentation or innovation promote

discretionary behaviour that is beyond formal job profiles. Such results are in line with Organ's (1983) postulate that organisational encouragement for innovation promotes OCB through greater engagement and satisfaction of the employee.

Apart from cultural values, organizational commitment was also found to be a predictor of OCB, particularly, affective and normative commitment emerged as strong predictors. These results revealed that employees who are emotionally bound to their organization and have internalized obligations have a greater tendency to engage in positive extra-role behavior. This can be said because OCB dimensions of defending and refraining were largely influenced by the commitment forms mentioned above. However, very little, even a negative impact of continuance commitment was observed, especially on refraining behaviour. This finding reinforces that staying in an organization for instrumental reasons does not promote genuine advocacy or citizenship behavior.

Hence, looking at the overall analysis of the results and discussions above, it may certainly be stated that cultural context does shape organisational citizenship behaviour. Moorman and Blakely (1995) examined individualism and collectivism as cultural orientations and found that employees with more collectivistic values were significantly more likely to demonstrate OCB than those with individualistic orientations. It highlights the importance of shared values and social cohesion in promoting extra-role behavior.

Bhuiyan and Menguc's (2002) research further showed that employees experiencing greater autonomy at work reported higher job satisfaction, which subsequently predicted OCB in a big way. This finding highlights Organ's (1983) model, which links job satisfaction with citizenship behaviour. Similarly, Anderson and Williams (1996) studied hospital nurses in their work setup and concluded that a combination of job autonomy and interdependence led to help-seeking, as well as helping behavior exhibiting that organizational structure interacts with cultural values to influence behaviour of employees.

In the Indian context, Mohanty and Rath (2012) examined manufacturing, IT, and banking employees. Their analysis revealed significant correlations between organisational culture dimensions-individual autonomy, conflict tolerance, structure, and support-and OCB components like altruism, conscientiousness, and civic virtue. Their findings affirm the critical role of culture in shaping citizenship behaviour.

Similarly, Kar and Tiwari (1999) found a causal relationship between cultural dimensions and OCB and its dimensions when studying employees from manufacturing units. These results empower the belief that organisational culture is not just a large, powerful, rigid structure but a complex interplay of values, structures, and relationships, each of which can differentially impact various aspects of OCB.

These results highlight the importance of cultural values-openness, trust, authenticity, proaction, autonomy, collaboration, and experimentation-in nurturing an environment favourable for OCB. The presence of affective and normative commitment further enhances these behaviours, while excessive hierarchy and continuance-based commitment tend to suppress them. An organisational culture that embraces these multidimensional constructs creates a fertile ground for employees to contribute to organisational success beyond their prescribed roles voluntarily.

Limitations and Future Directions

Apart from a relatively small sample size, this study did not take into account individual level antecedents of OCB like personality factors, which might be strongly influencing such extra role behavior. Analysis, in terms of different sectors and types of organisations could have yielded insights into the cross-sectionality of such a relationship, which could be a plausible future direction. Also, other dimensions of organisational culture besides values could be explored in future studies.

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